

Supporting Information

Mechanochemical Activation of Polymer-Embedded Photoluminescent Benzoxazole Moieties

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Experimental section

Materials

Unless otherwise stated, reagents and solvents were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich or TCI Europe and were used as received. The purification of 2,5-dimethoxyaniline was performed via sublimation under reduce pressure at 90°C. Unless otherwise noted, all reactions were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere.

Instrumentation

Bruker Avance III and Avance III HD spectrometers were used to record NMR spectra at 400 MHz (^1H) and 100 MHz (^{13}C). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS; however spectra were referenced against residual solvent proton peaks. A Biotage Isolera Flash system was used to perform flash silica gel chromatography using Biotage Flash Cartridges. Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) analysis were conducted at 30 °C using THF as the eluent. The measurements were conducted at a flow rate of 1.0 mL·min⁻¹ on an Agilent 1200 series HPLC system equipped with two Agilent PLgel mixed-D columns (ID = 7.5 mm, L = 300 mm, particle size = 5 μm). An Agilent PLgel mixed guard column (particle size = 5 μm) was further used. Signals were acquired by a UV detector (Agilent 1200 series), an Optilab REX interferometric refractometer, and a miniDawn TREOS light scattering detector (Wyatt Technology Corp.). Data processing was performed with Astra software (Wyatt Technology Corp.). Narrow-molecular-weight polystyrene (in the range of 2,340 - 364,000 g/mol) references were used for calibration. Photoluminescence spectra were recorded on a Horiba Fluorolog 3 spectrometer with right angle illumination geometry. A 450W Xenon source was used for excitation and detection was achieved by a FL-1030-UP photomultiplier. Relative quantum yields were determined using a protocol recommended by the IUPAC, with a solution of 9,10-diphenylanthracene in THF (QY = 0.94) as standard.^{1,2} A Shimadzu UV-2401PC spectrophotometer was used to record ultraviolet-

visible (UV-Vis) absorption spectra. A Branson Model 450 ultrasonic 1/2 in horn sonicator equipped with a 13 mm sonicator tip was used to perform all sonication experiments. A MX07R-20 refrigerating/heating bath from VWR was used to maintain a constant solution temperature during sonication experiments. Elemental analyses (EA) were performed on a CE Instruments EA 1110 by flash combustion and GC separation.

Synthesis protocols

Synthesis of (2,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-methoxybenzamide

A dry 250 mL round-bottomed flask (r.b.f.) was charged with 5.02 g (32.8 mmol) of 2,5-dimethoxyaniline and a magnetic stir bar. The atmosphere was then exchanged against N₂ by 3 evacuation/filling cycles, before 40 mL of dry THF and 5 mL of dry triethylamine (35.9 mmol) were added and dissolved the 2,5-dimethoxyaniline. A solution of 4.4 mL of 2-methoxybenzoyl chloride (5.04 g, 29.5 mmol) in 20 mL of dry THF was prepared in a 50 mL addition funnel and added dropwise into the stirred 2,5-dimethoxyaniline solution, which had been cooled with an ice bath to 0°C. After complete addition, the ice bath was removed and the reaction mixture was stirred for another 30 min at room temperature (r.t.). Distilled water (40 mL) was added and the mixture was acidified with aqueous HCl until a neutral pH was reached. The mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (200 mL), the organic phase was washed with brine (2 x 200 mL), dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The product was purified by flash silica gel column chromatography using a hexane/ethyl acetate gradient (25 - 70% of ethyl acetate) which, after solvent removal and drying in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight, afforded the title compound (8.07 g, 28.02 mmol, 95%) as an off-white solid.

¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 3.72 (3H, s), 3.91 (3H, s), 4.08(3H, s), 6.63 (1H, dd), 7.00 (1H, d), 7.15 (1H, t), 7.29 (1H, d), 7.60 (1H, t), 8.11 (1H, d), 8.18 (1H, d), 10.69 (1H, s); ¹³C

NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 55.33, 56.47, 56.63, 106.18, 107.34, 111.43, 112.66, 120.90, 121.23, 128.65, 131.37, 133.72, 142.27, 153.23, 157.18, 162.11; MS (ESI) m/z [$M + Na^+$] calcd. for (C₁₆H₁₇NO₄): 310.22, found: 310.1; m.p.: 84-86°C; EA calcd. for C₁₆H₁₇NO₄: C = 66.89%, H = 5.96%, N = 4.88%; found: C = 67.01%, H = 6.13%, N = 4.89%.

Synthesis of 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzo[d]oxazol-5-ol (1)

(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-2-methoxybenzamide (1.00 g, 3.48 mmol) and pyridine hydrochloride (2.00 g, 17.3 mmol) were placed in a 50 mL r.b.f. equipped with a condenser and a stir bar and the mixture was heated to 200°C under ambient atmosphere; the melted mixture was then magnetically stirred for 1 h. After cooling the reaction mixture to r.t., HCl 2M (10 mL) was added to the solid residue and the suspension was stirred for another 30 min at r.t. The reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (200 mL), the organic phase was washed with brine (2 x 200mL), dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification was performed by flash silica gel column chromatography using a hexane/ethyl acetate gradient (20 - 30 % of ethyl acetate) as eluent to obtain **1** (0.50 g, 2.20 mmol, 64%) as a white powder.

¹H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 6.91 (1H, dd), 7.10 (3H, m), 7.51 (1H, td), 7.61 (1H, d), 7.97 (1H, dd), 9.67 (1H, s), 11.27 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 104.10, 110.46, 111.04, 114.13, 117.12, 119.93, 127.24, 133.73, 140.28, 142.44, 155.39, 157.60, 162.69; MS (ESI) m/z [$M + H^+$] calcd. for (C₁₃H₉NO₃): 228.06, found: 228.0; m.p.: 215-217°C; EA calcd. for C₁₃H₉NO₃: C = 68.72%, H = 3.99%, N = 6.16%; found: C = 68.65%, H = 4.06%, N = 5.99%.

Synthesis of 2-(5-((2-bromo-2-methylpropanoyl)oxy)benzo[d]oxazol-2-yl)phenyl 2-bromo-2-methylpropanoate (2)

Compound **1** (100 mg, 0.44 mmol), dry THF (5 mL) and dry Et₃N (0.3 mL) were placed in a dry 50 mL r.b.f., and the magnetically stirred mixture was cooled in an ice-bath to 0°C, before

2-bromo-2-methylpropanoyl bromide (54 μ L, 0.45 mmol) was added dropwise at 0°C. After the addition was complete, the ice bath was removed and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at r.t. The reaction mixture was then diluted with ethyl acetate (100 mL), the organic phase was washed with brine (2 x 100 mL), dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification by flash silica gel column chromatography using a hexane/ethyl acetate gradient (5 - 15% of ethyl acetate) as eluent to yield compound **3** (158 mg, 0.30 mmol, 68%) as an off-white powder.

¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 2.08 (3H, s), 2.16 (3H, s), 7.27 (1H, dd), 7.42 (1H, d), 7.60 (1H, t), 7.65 (1H, d), 7.77 (1H, td), 7.89 (1H, d), 8.31 (1H, dd); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆, ppm): δ = 30.08, 30.43, 55.76, 56.97, 111.58, 112.61, 119.24, 119.43, 123.53, 127.41, 130.22, 133.67, 141.67, 147.51, 147.55, 148.52, 160.49, 169.56, 169.91; MS (ESI) *m/z* [M + H⁺] calcd. for (C₂₁H₁₉Br₂NO₅): 524.96, found: 526.0; m.p.: 115-117°C; EA calcd. for C₂₁H₁₉Br₂NO₅: C = 48.03%, H = 3.65%, N = 2.67%; found: C = 48.04%, H = 3.85%, N = 2.89%.

Synthesis of model compounds 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzo[d]oxazol-5-yl acetate (3**) and 2-(5-acetoxybenzo[d]oxazol-2-yl)phenyl acetate (**4**)**

Compound **1** (201 mg, 0.88 mmol) and a magnetic stir bar were placed in a dry 50 mL r.b.f, **1** was dissolved in a mixture of dry THF (5 mL), and dry Et₃N (0.3 mL), and the solution was cooled on an ice bath. Then, acetyl chloride (0.2 mL, 2.6 mmol) was added dropwise at 0°C to the stirred solution, the ice bath was removed, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3h at r.t. The reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (200 mL), the organic phase was washed with brine (2 x 200 mL), dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Purification by flash column chromatography on silica with a hexane/ethyl acetate gradient (5 - 20% of ethyl acetate) yielded compounds **3** (r.f.: 0.46, 57 mg, 0.21 mmol, 24 %) and **4** (r.f.: 0.19, 195 mg, 0.62 mmol, 70%), both as white solids.

3: ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 2.32 (3H, s), 7.11 (2H, m), 7.25 (1H, dd), 7.53 (1H, td), 7.65 (1H, d), 7.65 (1H, d), 7.86 (1H, d), 8.01 (1H, dd), 11.07 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 20.84, 110.44, 111.26, 112.57, 117.27, 119.85, 119.93, 127.85, 134.11, 140.17, 146.55, 147.79, 157.80, 163.58, 169.43; MS (ESI) m/z [$\text{M} - \text{H}^+$] calcd. for ($\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4$): 269.07, found: 268.0; m.p.: 155-157°C; EA calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4$: C = 66.91%, H = 4.12%, N = 5.20%; found: C = 66.57%, H = 4.55%, N = 4.85%.

4: ^1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 2.31 (3H, s), 2.42 (3H, s), 7.23 (1H, dd), 7.38 (1H, dd), 7.53 (1H, td), 7.64 (1H, d), 7.71 (1H, td), 7.85 (1H, d), 8.26 (1H, dd), 11.07 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , ppm): δ = 20.81, 20.99, 111.16, 113.33, 119.46, 120.05, 124.43, 126.81, 129.92, 133.35, 141.61, 147.29, 147.63, 148.95, 160.64, 169.45; MS (ESI) m/z [$\text{M} - \text{H}^+$] calcd. for ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_5$): 335.08, found 334.1; m.p.: 142-144°C; EA calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_5$: C = 65.59%, H = 4.21%, N = 4.50%; found: C = 65.86%, H = 4.29%, N = 4.47%.

Synthesis of Bz-PMA

Initiator **2** (9.7 mg, 0.02 mmol) and Cu(0) powder (5.2 mg, 0.08 mmol) were placed in a 25 mL Schlenk flask equipped with a magnetic stir bar and the atmosphere was exchanged against N_2 by 3 evacuation/filling cycles, before a solution of Me_6TREN (22 μL , 0.08 mmol) in dry DMSO (2 mL) was added. Methyl acrylate (2.3 mL, 26 mmol), which had been passed through a basic aluminum oxide pad and been sparged with argon for 15 min, was introduced into the Schlenk flask and three freeze-pump-thaw cycles were performed. The polymerization mixture was then stirred at r.t. for 1 h. To quench the reaction, the Schlenk flask was opened to air and frozen in liquid nitrogen. The reaction mixture was dissolved in THF (20 mL) and filtered through a short silica pad before precipitation in cold methanol (500 mL). The product was collected by filtration, and re-precipitated from THF (20 mL) into cold methanol (500 mL). The product was collected by filtration, and dried in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight, which left a viscous, sticky, colorless solid (2.13 g).

^1H NMR (CDCl_3): $\delta = 1.46\text{-}1.77$ (2H, m), 2.22 (1H, m), 3.58 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3): $\delta = 34.31, 40.77, 51.49, 174.32$; SEC $M_n = 107.2$ kg/mol, $\bar{D} = 1.13$; EA calcd. for $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_2)_{1200} + \text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{Br}_2\text{NO}_5$: C = 55.77%, H = 7.01%, N=0.01%; found: C = 55.92%, H = 7.23%.

General procedure for the sonication experiments

The solutions were prepared by dissolving the polymer (20 mg) in THF (20 mL) and the mixtures were stirred for 30 min. The polymer solution (17 mL) was placed in a Suslick cell, and the latter was placed into a temperature controlled bath at 0°C . Air was removed by sparging the solution with nitrogen for 20 min. Then, pulses of 0.5 s ultrasound, intercalated with 1 s rest periods, at an intensity of 10.4 W/cm^2 were applied to the polymer solution. After 0, 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 min aliquots of $300 \mu\text{L}$ were taken from the solution and diluted with THF ($300 \mu\text{L}$ each) to record photoluminescence spectra of each sample. To allow SEC analyses, the solvent was removed from the samples by drying in a vacuum oven at 40°C overnight and the residues were dissolved in THF ($300 \mu\text{L}$).

NMR spectra

Figure S1: ¹H NMR spectrum of (2,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-methoxybenzamide in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S2: ¹³C NMR spectrum of (2,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-methoxybenzamide in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S3: ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 1 in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S4: ¹³C NMR spectrum of compound 1 in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S5: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **2** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S6: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **2** in DMSO-d₆.

Figure S7: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **3** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S8: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **3** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S9: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **4** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S10: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **4** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S11: ^1H NMR spectrum of compound **Bz-PMA** in DMSO-d_6 .

Figure S12: ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **Bz-PMA** in DMSO-d_6 .

Mass spectrometry

Figure S13: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of (2,5-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-methoxybenzamide.

Figure S14: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum positive (top) and negative (bottom) mode of compound **1**.

Figure S15: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound 2.

Figure S16: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound 3.

Figure S17: Electrospray ionization mass spectrum of compound 4.

Sonication experiments

SEC characterization

Figure S18: Evolution of the ratio of the number-average molecular weight (M_n) and the initial number-average molecular weight $M_{n,0}$ after ultrasonically treating a 1 mg/mL THF solution of **Bz-MPA** for the times indicated. The graph shows data from three separate experiment series.

Figure S19: Representative size-exclusion chromatograms (refractive index signals) acquired upon ultrasonicating a dilute THF solution of PMA and **4** ($c = 1 \text{ mg/mL}$ and $c = 9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol/L}$) for the times indicated.

Figure S20: Evolution of the ratio of the number-average molecular weight (M_n) and the initial number-average molecular weight $M_{n,0}$ after ultrasonicating a THF solution of PMA and **4** ($c = 1 \text{ mg/mL}$ and $c = 9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol/L}$) for the times indicated. The graph shows data from three separate experiment series.

Figure S21: Determination of the chain scission rate constants for **Bz-PMA** (black) and PMA in presence of **4** (red). The graph shows the evolution of a function of the number-average molecular weight (M_n) and the initial number-average molecular weight $M_{n,0}$ after ultrasonication of THF solutions of **Bz-PMA** (1 mg/mL) and PMA and **4** ($c = 1$ mg/mL and $c = 9 \times 10^{-6}$ mol/L) for the times indicated. Symbols represent experimental averages from three separate experiments and error bars indicate the standard deviation. Lines represent linear fits of the data that were obtained by constraining the function to go through the origin.

UV-Vis absorption spectra

Figure S22: UV-vis absorption spectra of a dilute solution of **Bz-PMA** in THF ($c = 1$ mg/mL) before (black) and after ultrasonication for 60 minutes (red). This experiment was carried out independently and no aliquots were taken during sonication. Then 3 mL of each solution were concentrated and re-dissolved in 1 mL of THF to record UV-Vis spectra.

Photoluminescence data

Figure S23: Representative photoluminescence spectra ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 340$ nm) recorded after ultrasonication of a dilute THF solution of PMA and **4** ($c = 1$ mg/mL and $c = 9 \times 10^{-6}$ mol/L) for the times indicated.

Figure S24: Evolution of the photoluminescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 340$ nm) at 500 nm after ultrasonication of a THF solution of PMA and **4** ($c = 1$ mg/mL and $c = 9 \times 10^{-6}$ mol/L) for the times indicated. The graph shows data from three separate experiment series.

Figure S25: Evolution of the photoluminescence intensity ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 340 \text{ nm}$) at 500 nm after ultrasonication of a 1 mg/mL THF solution of **Bz-PMA** for the times indicated. The graph shows data from three separate experiment series.

Figure S26: Evolution of the ratio of the photoluminescence intensity (PL) and the initial photoluminescence intensity (PL_0 , $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 340 \text{ nm}$) at 370 nm after ultrasonication of a 1 mg/mL THF solution of **Bz-PMA** for the times indicated. Data points are averages of three separate experiment series.

Figure S27: Evolution of normalized $M_n/M_{n,0}$ (data from Figure 2b) and normalized photoluminescence intensity recorded at 500 nm (data from Figure 3b) and 370 nm (data from Figure S26). Data were normalized to a scale of 1 to 0, with 1 representing the initial value and 0 the value obtained after 60 min of ultrasonication. Data were fitted with a first order exponential decay function to obtain decay constant k_d for each dataset.

References

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